

D2.3 End report on FAIR training resources

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a concise overview of ELIXIR’s activities to advance the curation of RDM training resources during 2024–2025. While TeSS is the main aggregator of training materials, gaps in metadata consistency and incomplete coverage across Nodes limit the ability to produce a comprehensive report on FAIR and RDM training resources across ELIXIR.

The deliverables findings and conclusions draw on:

- The workshops delivered under Milestone M2.3,
- Follow-up work through the RDM Trainer Network
- Platform and curation challenges identified
- Findings from a small user-testing exercise designed to gather practical evidence

The findings from the small user-testing exercise reinforce earlier workshop conclusions that improving RDM training curation in TeSS depends less on changing community understanding, and more on clearer guidance, improved interface design and stronger use of structured annotation where available.

Improving FAIR and RDM training curation and discoverability requires both platform development and more explicit community guidance, both in TeSS and across ELIXIR Communities.

This resource is intended for TeSS developers, the ELIXIR Interoperability platform and training curators from all ELIXIR Communities.

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1. Background and introduction

Training in research data management (RDM) is produced by many ELIXIR Nodes and Communities and indexed in TeSS to increase discoverability. TeSS aggregates materials from a wide range of providers but relies on voluntary metadata submission, which introduces variability in coverage and quality.

While FAIR principles can apply to training resources, TeSS does not currently mandate the metadata required to assess FAIRness, such as licence information, versioning, persistent identifiers, or standardised topic annotation. EDAM ontology could be used in TeSS to support consistent classification of training topics and operations, alongside complementary annotation of related tools and resources,

thanks to the integration with FAIRsharing and bio.tools. Still, EDAM, bio.tools and FAIRsharing use remains inconsistent and incomplete, particularly for RDM-related materials, where RDM concepts have only been introduced recently.

As a result, it is not feasible to produce a quantitative or comprehensive evaluation of training resources on RDM and FAIR topics in TeSS. Instead, this deliverable focuses on evaluating the current state of curation of RDM training resources indexed in TeSS, including metadata completeness, usability and alignment with FAIR-aligned machine-actionable discoverability.

2. Summary of activities (2024–2025)

2.1 September 2024 workshop (M2.3)

In September 2024, Alexander Botzki and Federico Bianchini led a workshop on FAIRification of RDM materials titled “[RDM training annotation: strategies for improved curation in TeSS](#)”, coordinated by Xenia Perez Sitja as the co-lead of the RDM Trainer Network (part of the RDM Community).

40 people from different ELIXIR Nodes attended the event to improve the curation of training materials in [TeSS \(ELIXIR’s Training Portal\)](#). The workshop brought together the work from different areas of ELIXIR: Interoperability Platform, Training Platform, FAIR Training Focus Group, and the RDM Community.

With over 500 RDM-related training materials in TeSS, effective curation is essential to enhance visibility within ELIXIR and beyond, including integration into resources such as the RDMkit and the creation of learning paths. Therefore, the topic of training curation is both relevant and timely. Several projects in ELIXIR have been working on core ELIXIR resources for curation, such as FAIRsharing and bio.tools, and others are adding terminology to the EDAM ontology for curating training materials in TeSS and sharing best practices for training annotation.

The workshop presentation was recorded for visibility and reusability and shared publicly on the [ELIXIR YouTube Channel](#) and [Website](#). The slides from the workshop were also published on Zenodo and linked to various ELIXIR Communities on Zenodo:

Bianchini, F., Botzki, A., Helena, R., & Pérez Sitjà, X. (2024, December 20). RDM training annotation: strategies for improved curation in TeSS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534996>

2.2 December 2024 Luxembourg meeting

The RDM Community meeting revisited annotation practices, EDAM extensions, and user feedback. Ongoing work with FAIR Cookbook contributors demonstrated how training curation connects to broader knowledge resources. This piece of work will result in a FAIR Cookbook recipe as part of other ELIXIR work.

2.3 User-testing exercise

A small user-testing activity was carried out at the end of 2025 to complement workshop discussions with practical evidence. Four volunteers were asked to curate the same three RDM training materials in TeSS and complete a short reflective questionnaire.

This exercise follows established usability-testing approaches, in which a small sample (5–7 participants) is sufficient to identify common barriers and inconsistencies.

The exercise aimed to examine:

- How consistently do different users annotate the same resource, and use the EDAM ontology
- Metadata fields perceived as unclear or incomplete
- Barriers encountered when curating RDM-specific content
- Differences in the interpretation of “RDM training”
- Perceived gaps in TeSS guidance and interface support

Methodology

This activity provides a qualitative snapshot of current curation practices and helps identify where guidance, documentation and platform improvements would most benefit users.

Because TeSS does not allow editing entries owned by other users (unless the user is a “curator”), the exercise used the “Register new training material” form to simulate curation. Participants filled out the form without submitting it and recorded their decisions through screenshots or structured templates.

A screenshot of a web browser showing the 'New material' form in the TeSS application. The browser address bar shows 'tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/new'. The form is titled 'New material' and includes several sections: 'Show this material?' with a checkbox and a note about visibility; 'Title' and 'URL' fields; a 'Description' field with a note that it supports markdown; 'Resource types' with a dropdown and a plus icon; 'Scientific topics' with a text input and a plus icon; and 'Keywords' at the bottom. On the right side, there are two informational boxes: 'What are training materials?' explaining that training materials are links to online content, and 'Locking fields' explaining that some fields are automatically updated and cannot be overwritten.

Limitations

TeSS currently applies EDAM only to “Scientific Topics” and “Operations”. However, “Keywords” remain free text, which leads to inconsistent naming and reduced control.

TeSS does not currently support expressing “training about training” (e.g. methodologies for designing training, how to create FAIR training), limiting accurate representation of a significant subset of ELIXIR training materials.

This user testing does not take into consideration the automatic indexing feature for TeSS using Bioschemas.

Reviewer profile and diversity of perspectives

The user-testing exercise involved a small but mixed group of curators, selected to reflect variation in experience with TeSS, familiarity with EDAM, and confidence in annotating RDM training.

	Prior TeSS submissions	EDAM familiarity	Confidence annotating RDM
Reviewer A	<3	Basic	Low (2/5)
Reviewer B	>10	Intermediate	High (4/5)
Reviewer C	>10	Intermediate	Moderate (3/5)
Reviewer D	>10	Basic	High (4/5)

Although the group was small, the reviewers represented diverse levels of confidence and familiarity with EDAM, allowing comparison not only of annotation choices.

Summary of findings

Consistency across reviewers

Despite differences in experience and conceptual framing, reviewers showed strong convergence in the terminology used when structured options (i.e. “Scientific topic”, “Operations”) were used:

- Reviewers independently selected the same small set of high-level concepts, particularly around FAIR data, data management, and closely related RDM themes. For example, FAIR data, data management.
- Where EDAM Scientific Topics were used, reviewers tended to converge on identical or near-identical terms. For instance, all picked FAIR data for the courses related to this scientific field.
- When EDAM “Operations” were applied, reviewers selected similar terms (e.g. data management planning, data deposition).

This suggests that conceptual agreement exists within the RDM community and that variation arises primarily from constraints on guidance and design rather than from disagreement about content meaning.

However, reviewers noted that limited term visibility and specificity can encourage repeated use of broad terms (e.g. FAIR data, data management, open science), which risks making conceptually distinct terms feel interchangeable in practice.

Differences compared with original TeSS entries

Compared with the original TeSS entries, reviewer annotations showed systematic differences:

- **Shift from keywords to structured fields**
Concepts originally expressed only as free-text keywords were frequently moved into standardised, structured Scientific Topics when possible. For instance, “Data Management” in “Scientific Topic” substitutes several “Keywords” (RDM, data management, research data management).

Scientific topics 📌

- Data management http://edamontology.org/topic_3071 ✕

Add a new scientific topic

- **Reduction in semantic duplication**
Reviewers most familiarised with EDAM avoided repeating the same concepts across keywords and structured fields, while less familiarised reviewers duplicated information as a precaution to

retain findability. Those who used keywords added variability and inconsistency with capitalisation and used different terms as open-ended text that may already exist in other forms or in “Scientific Topics” and “Operations” as structured metadata fields.

Keywords

FAIR Data	X	Data Management	X	Open Science	X
FAIR	X	Reusability	X	Reproducibility	X
data repositories	X		X		+

- **Use of “Operations” and FAIRsharing/bio.tools annotations**

“Operations” were absent from original entries but were introduced by 3/4 reviewers (those who indicated higher confidence annotating RDM training). FAIRsharing and Bio.tools annotations were also extremely relevant for some of the tested entries, which originally lacked any links to external resources.

External resources

FASTQ Sequence and Sequer	https://fairsharing.org/10.25	X
Minimum Information about	https://fairsharing.org/10.25	X
Minimal Information about a	https://fairsharing.org/10.25	X
European Nucleotide Archivi	https://fairsharing.org/10.25	X
ArrayExpress	https://fairsharing.org/10.25	X
FastQC	https://bio.tools/tool/fastqc	X

- **No increase in diversity of terms.**

Reviewers did not introduce substantially new or conflicting terminology; instead, if there was any divergence or diversity added, it came from duplication of terms in the “keywords” field.

Overall, reviewer annotations were more aligned than the originals, even though completeness varied across reviewers.

Keywords as a sign of uncertainty

- Reviewers less familiarised with EDAM relied on keywords as a fallback mechanism to ensure visibility of training.
- More familiarised reviewers deliberately avoided keywords, citing their lack of control and limited added value.
- Importantly, the words used as keywords largely overlapped with “Scientific Topics” or “Operations” chosen.

- Two reviewers also reported that TeSS does not clearly indicate which fields rely on controlled vocabularies versus free-text input, leading to duplication of information and inconsistent annotation strategies. One reviewer did not complete the “operations” fields due to the lack of information about what this term referred to.

Operations

Add a new operation

Insights on non-RDM-related fields

While the user-testing exercise focused on RDM-related curation fields (Scientific Topics, Operations, External resources links, keywords), reviewers consistently highlighted several non-RDM-specific issues affecting all training materials in TeSS.

1. **Provenance and attribution are weakly supported.** Authorship and contribution are represented as free-text, without persistent identifiers or clear differentiation of roles:
 - a. Content provider vs authors/contributors
 - b. Associated projects, funders
 - c. Nodes and content providers

Content provider

Authors

Contributors

2. **Training maturity and status are not clearly represented.** The distinction between draft or ready is semantically important for reuse and learning path construction. In several cases, reviewers explicitly changed the status of entries to avoid presenting early-stage materials as ready to use, indicating that status should be treated as a meaningful field rather than a purely administrative one.
3. **Access conditions are not clearly communicated.** When materials are behind authentication or required enrolment, this was not clearly indicated in the TeSS entries. Reviewers reported this as a barrier to usability.
4. **Granularity of training materials is insufficient.** Entire workshops, playlists, or collections are often represented as single entries. Reviewers highlighted that this aggregation has limitations:
 - a. Discoverability and reuse of individual materials.
 - b. And therefore, meaningful construction of learning paths.
5. **Inconsistent and uncontrolled terminology in multiple fields.** Fields such as “resource type” and “target audience” are not controlled vocabularies. Reviewers observed significant variation in spelling, capitalisation, plurality and meaning, reducing search precision and consistency. For instance, “course materials” and “Course materials” are treated as two separate entries for “Resource type”, making filtering materials more difficult.

Interpretation

Taken together, the user-testing exercise shows that:

1. Reviewers largely agree on how RDM and FAIR content-related concepts should be used/applied to annotate/curate RDM training materials.
2. Inconsistencies in curation arise when TeSS relies on free text (Keywords, Resource Type) or poorly explained fields (Operations).
3. Structured vocabularies (for RDM training resources and in general) promote convergence, but their partial implementation due to a lack of guidance, and the use of free-text fields limit the impact.
4. Differences between original entries and reviewer annotations are systematic and predictable: reviewers enter the same terms (e.g. FAIR data) and diverge on additional, more granular ones (e.g., data deposition, data management plans).
5. TeSS currently lacks mechanisms to actively flag inaccessible materials or that an entry should be improved.

Implications

All findings from the user-testing exercise reinforce earlier conclusions from RDM Community meetings and workshops that improving RDM training curation in TeSS depends less on changing community understanding and more on clearer guidance, improved interface design, and stronger use of structured annotation where available.

[Current guidance is available via the Training Platform](#), but uptake remains low.

3. Conclusion and recommendations

From TeSS development side, significant progress has been made in community alignment, curation awareness and cross-platform collaboration (e.g FAIRsharing, bio.tools, bioschemas). However, as noted at the start of this report, the current TeSS ecosystem limits the ability to provide a comprehensive overview of FAIR training resources.

All activities carried out as part of the DATAREX Commissioned Service regarding curation of RDM training materials point out that **improving FAIR and RDM training requires both platform development** (recommendations for TeSS 3.1) **and more explicit community guidance** (recommendations for communities 3.2).

3.1 Platform-level recommendations (TeSS)

1. Improve field guidance and interface clarity

Provide inline explanations for all fields, clarify the purpose of structured versus free-text fields, and reorder the submission form to group key fields adequately. This includes relocating fields such as “Node” to sit alongside content provider information, rather than under publication/time stamp metadata.

Reviewers also highlighted inconsistent interaction patterns across fields (e.g., dropdowns, buttons, free-text inputs), which increase cognitive load and contribute to missed or incomplete annotations.

Reviewers used workarounds to select Scientific Topics (e.g., typing letters) because there was no link to browse the full vocabulary and because triggering help text was difficult.

Scientific topics 📄

- Anatomy
- Analytical chemistry
- Allergy, clinical immunology and immunotherapeutics
- Anaesthesiology
- Applied mathematics
- Animal study
- Agricultural science
- Antimicrobial resistance
- Acoustics

2. Strengthen provenance and attribution mechanisms

Introduce structured fields for training provider, project and funder, and improve author/contributor representation beyond free text.

3. Make access conditions explicit

Clearly indicate when materials require authentication, enrollment or restricted access.

4. Support finer-grained representation of training materials

Enable clearer distinction between collections, workshops, playlists and individual resources, and use structured metadata instead of free text for “Resource Type”.

5. Generally, reduce reliance on uncontrolled vocabularies (free text)

Introduce controlled vocabularies or stronger guidance for fields such as resource type and target audience.

Provide normalisation guidance (capitalisation, singular/plural) and/or enforce normalised variants to avoid fragmentation of filtering fields.

6. Improve EDAM usability for RDM curation

Enhance search (including synonyms), clarify the scope of “Scientific Topics” and “Operations”, and make “Operations” more visible (place at the top of the form).

Provide direct links to browse the full controlled vocabularies used (e.g. EDAM) and clearly label the provenance of suggestions (ontology-backed vs free text). Discourage the use of free-text unless strictly necessary.

7. Leverage integrations

Where possible, populate metadata from other sources (e.g. FAIRsharing, bio.tools) to reduce duplication and improve quality. For instance, using bio.tools annotation brings in the EDAM terms associated with the tool entry. Users cannot possibly know this feature with the current

design, and such fields sit at the bottom of the form.

External resources

Suggested policies, standards and databases to associate with this resource

Suggested tools to associate with this resource

 Add manually if no results are found

8. Missed opportunities for integration.

Reviewers reported that duplicating metadata entry across Zenodo (for DOIs) and TeSS is demotivating, and expressed a preference for stronger Zenodo-to-TeSS integration or harvesting to reduce duplication and improve sustainability.

3.2 Community-level recommendations (Nodes, Platforms, Communities)

1. Improve baseline submission quality

Encourage content owners to provide licences, access information and provenance at the point of submission.

2. Develop and promote shared curation guidance

Consolidate guidance through the RDM Trainer Network and Training Platform, including examples of good practice.

3. Create community-specific guidance for curating materials. Where possible, train communities to curate their content using a standardised method that meets their needs. E.g make communities aware of the extent of “Scientific Topics” related to that community that could be used to curate their materials.

4. Outcomes and expected impact

This deliverable provides a brief assessment of how RDM training resources are currently curated in TeSS, based on workshop discussions and a small user-testing exercise. The primary outcome is a clearer understanding of the metadata gaps, usability issues and differing curation practices that affect the visibility of RDM training across ELIXIR.

The work highlights where TeSS supports structured annotation (e.g. Topics and Operations) and where limitations remain, especially around licensing, contributors, versioning, and reliance on free-text keywords. The findings directly inform community guidance and future improvements needed in TeSS to support more consistent and discoverable materials.

Expected impact/outcomes include:

- Better shared understanding of how RDM training is currently indexed across ELIXIR;
- Evidence to guide Nodes in improving metadata when contributing to TeSS;
- Clearer requirements for training curation workflows within the RDM Community;
- Input to future platform development discussions between the Training and Interoperability Platforms.

5. Dissemination plans

The final report will be published openly on Zenodo, following ELIXIR's Commissioned Service guidelines. It will also be shared with the RDM Community and relevant Platform groups to support ongoing work on training curation and metadata guidance.